

NEID: Back On-Sky and Delivering Science Led by Early Career Researchers

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NEID PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS BY CAREER STAGE

Figure 1: Breakdown of unique NEID PIs by career stage at the time of their first successful NEID proposal from Semesters 2021B–2023A. This does not include successful repeat proposals. Over 85% of NEID PIs are either graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, or early career faculty/staff (defined as being within 10 years of their PhD).
Credit: Figure provided by author.

NEID is an extreme precision radial velocity (EPRV) spectrometer at the WIYN 3.5m Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory. It resumed science operations in November 2022, following a shutdown due to the June 2022 Contreras Fire at Kitt Peak National Observatory. We are pleased to report that NEID is still delivering radial velocities at the sub-m/s precision levels that it achieved before the fire.

NEID continues to be WIYN's flagship newest instrument, utilizing more than 75% of the available WIYN 3.5m Telescope time in Semester 2023A. It is scheduled for a similar percentage of Semester 2023B time after the NN-EXPLORE (NASA-NSF Exoplanet Observational Research) program received the largest number of NEID proposals to date.

Much of the awarded NEID time is being led by early career principal investigators (PIs). As shown in Figure 1, over 85% of the NEID PIs through Semester 2023A were either graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, or early career faculty/staff (defined as being within 10 years of their PhD) when they were first awarded time with NEID.

In early 2023, these early career PIs published several articles presenting NEID science results. These publications have reported on the usage of NEID to confirm and measure the masses of hot Jupiter-sized exoplanets discovered using NASA's *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite* (*TESS*) around both low-mass and solar-type stars [1, 2], to confirm and characterize a *TESS*-discovered and highly eccentric warm Jupiter (Figure 2, TOI-4127b; 3), and to probe the formation mechanism(s) of a warm sub-Saturn (TOI-1842b; 4) and a young, warm Neptune (TOI-1842b; 5).

Figure 2: This plot shows planet eccentricity for all known transiting planets with well-defined mass measurements vs. distance from the host star. TOI-4127b is indicated with a red star and is one of only a few known transiting planets at high eccentricity. The dashed red line shows how the orbit of TOI-4127b would become circular, assuming a constant angular momentum. The planet is not expected to reach a circular orbit during the main-sequence lifetime of its host star.
Credit: Gupta et al. 2023

References

- [1] Cañas, C. et al. 2023, *ApJ*, 166, 30. doi:10.3847/1538-3881/acdac7
- [2] Yee, S. W. et al. 2023, 265, 1. doi:10.3847/1538-4365/aca286
- [3] Gupta, A. F. et al. 2023, *AJ*, 165, 234. doi:10.3847/1538-3881/accb9b
- [4] Hixenbaugh, K. et al. 2023, *ApJL*, 949, 35. doi:10.3847/2041-8213/acd6f5
- [5] Frazier, R. C. et al. 2023, 944, L41. doi:10.3847/2041-8213/acba18